

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CONSTRUCTION SECTOR CHALLENGES AND RELEVANT LEGISLATIVE PROVISION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10955811>

Abstract

Energy efficiency of buildings is an important aspect of the green economy. Green building is a component of significant importance. The article discusses decisions taken at the legislative level in Georgia in this direction, relevant regulatory decisions, necessary emergency measures to ensure energy efficiency of buildings, as well as expectations and their significance in If proper results are achieved in this direction, the goal is to guarantee the energy efficiency of the proposed buildings, in our case throughout the country.

Keywords: *Energy efficiency, action plan, climate zone map. Heat transfer coefficient, energy labeling.*

In view of the nearest and extremely important challenge in the country, in order to ensure appropriate results in the direction of energy efficiency, the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (EESP) for 2019-2029 was prepared. In 2014, Georgia signed the association agreement with the European Union, the agreement recognizes the obligation to introduce new technologies and promote the development of energy efficiency. In order to significantly reduce energy consumption in the construction sector. In order to ensure the desired result in activities in the mentioned direction, Georgia undertakes to bring the national laws into compliance with Eurocash legislation, as a result, to ensure the process of reflecting the energy efficiency directive of buildings in the national legislation. The reform of the legal regulatory framework for the energy characteristics of buildings provided for by the Association Agreements of Georgia with the European Union is underway within the framework of the neighborhood program of the Danish government launched on the basis of the agreement between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark and the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia, and the process is also supported by the EU4energy technical assistance program project - "Legislative acts of Georgia regulating the energy consumption of buildings" Analysis and preparation of the draft law on energy efficiency of buildings" In 2020, the law "On energy efficiency" was adopted, according to which it was explained:

- Energy efficiency policy and its measures - National target indicator of energy saving
- measurement and verification system,
- Obligations defined for administrative bodies in order to promote the development of the energy market,
- Energy efficiency policy and relevant measures for buildings, including those used by administrative bodies,
- Energy efficiency policy in agriculture. Ensuring energy efficiency together with the law requires a number of measures that fully take into account the directives adopted in this direction in Europe, methods and technologies implemented. For this purpose, the Resolution of the Government of Georgia No. 354 of

July 13, 2021 was adopted. The resolution "On approval of minimum requirements for energy efficiency of buildings, parts of buildings or elements of buildings" determined:

- Categories and subcategories of buildings for the purpose of applying the minimum requirements of energy characteristics:

- List of settlements in Georgia according to common climate zone assigned to municipalities;
- Requirements for minimum energy characteristics of structural elements of buildings

The resolution presents a map of construction-climatic zones of Georgia.

The decree explains that for new buildings/parts of buildings of all categories and subcategories, as well as for existing buildings/parts of buildings, the design and construction

Requirements for building elements are defined at two levels. Of particular importance is the fact that in drawing up the guidelines, the maximum permissible heat transfer coefficients U_{max} of each element of the thermal envelope of a building structure, depending on climatic zones. The value of the maximum permissible total heat transfer coefficient $\bar{U}_{max}$ for the elements of the thermal envelope of a building is presented in the creation: Five main determining factors taken into account when preparing the regulatory framework for energy efficiency: - decarbonization; - Instead of financing energy imports, invest in the local economy and job creation, as a result of which 1 GWh of seasonal annual energy will release 20-50 thousand euros. -Energy security – reducing energy dependence. - Reducing emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) and other environmental pollutants. -Commitment to the European Union/Transformation and implementation of DA legislation in accordance with the commitments made in the Energy Union Treaty. Energy efficiency in construction, taking into account all factors, is combined in an approach known in Europe as “green building”, the first official steps in this direction were taken by enterprises in 1972, since then the European Parliament has adopted several dozen Basic Directives of the European Union relating to green energy in Europe are: - Energy

Efficiency Directive. and building performance - Energy Labeling Directive - Ecodesign Directive The above-mentioned directives are also linked to the Renewable Energy Directive, as well as regulations on the development of sustainable energy and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. carbonization – has two key elements: emissions and emissions reduction;

- Renewable energy sources.

Around the world, the issue of climate change is discussed/monitored by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

Due to the fact that Georgia is not a country included in Annex 1 of the UNFCCC, it has the right to participate in only one of the three mechanisms provided for by the Kyoto Protocol - the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM).

On September 25, 2015, Georgia submitted the Nationally Determined Contribution document to the UNFCCC secretariat, the goal of which was to unconditionally reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 15% by 2030 according to the Business as Usual (BAU) concept. The document notes that the 15% reduction target could be raised to 25% under certain conditions, depending on global agreement on the importance of technical cooperation in accessing low-cost financial resources and sharing technological expertise. A 25% reduction in emissions under the BAU scenario ensures that Georgia's greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 will be 40% lower than in 1990. Along with the preparation

of the legislative framework in order to achieve the appropriate result in this direction, a significant problem is ensuring public awareness and training of personnel with appropriate qualifications. Training programs are provided for by law, which is taken into account by law. retraining of personnel in the relevant area. The Government of Georgia approves training programs in accordance with the EESG, on the proposal of the Ministry, in accordance with the EESG: for suppliers; b) for energy audit performers in industry; c) for persons carrying out energy efficiency certification of buildings; d) for energy managers and installers of elements that affect the energy consumption of a building. A list of experts trained under the training program is compiled by the Ministry and published on its website. Taking these tasks into account, at Akaki Tsereteli State University there is a training course “Green Construction” in the bachelor’s degree in the field of construction, and literature in the doctoral program “Energy Efficient Technologies in Construction”

References:

1. Energy Efficiency Law and the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan A brief overview of the main issues of the Energy Efficiency Law and EESG July 3, 2019
file:///C:/Users/admin/Desktop/5_20190701_presentation_on_ee_law_and_neeap_geo.pdf
2. National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan
3. Law on Energy Efficiency.